

TRANSPORTATION PROBLEMS IN UZBEKISTAN

Choriyeva Malika

1st year doctoral student of Tashkent State Transport University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185975>

It is not a secret to any of us that in the territory of Uzbekistan educational buildings, various socio-economic objects, in general, around areas with a lot of traffic are considered very dangerous and scary for the drivers of vehicles, and for the lives of pedestrians who move around the above area or have to cross the roads. Especially the roads around pre-school educational institutions and schools are dangerous for the lives of mothers, children and students. We all know that as a solution to this, one person from those organizations goes out and waves hand-made colorful flags to mothers, children and students moving between regions in order to ensure the safe movement of the children. However, it is an unpleasant situation for an employee working in those organizations to spend extra time, or to perform the above task by spending extra time in addition to his duties. Such controlled actions are unpleasant, tiring and time-consuming for pedestrians, drivers, and the driver (whose original profession is a teacher or kindergarten worker).

Motor vehicles remain a major source of air pollution, especially in areas with heavy traffic. The air pollutants emitted by the exhaust gases emitted by the vehicle as a result of long-term stoppage of the vehicle driven by the driver are: carbon monoxide (CO); nitrogen oxide (NO₂); particulate matter; volatile organic compounds. The above emissions can cause smog, heart and lung diseases and cancer. Motor vehicles are the biggest source of air pollution. In order to help reduce air pollution, we need to use modern and effective methods. You can reduce vehicle pollution if: If we use less means of transport; If we drive a less polluting vehicle; If we do not keep the vehicle on fire for a long time; If we drive the vehicle wisely. Car pollutants seriously harm our health and cause climate change. Combustion of gasoline and diesel fuel produces harmful byproducts such as nitrogen dioxide, carbon monoxide, hydrocarbons, benzene, and formaldehyde. It is also the most common emission of carbon dioxide by vehicles. In addition to the above cases, many traffic accidents occur as a result of the disorderly movement of vehicles and pedestrians. The reason is that in order to quickly reach the pedestrian destination, pedestrians try to cross the road shorter without going to the crosswalk and traffic lights. But it often happens that the driver controls the speed of the vehicle by aiming at the traffic light, and it is difficult to reduce the speed sharply. Because of this, how many families are forced to stay without breadwinners, and how many families have to stay with disabled children. Of course, we cannot say that all the fault lies with the driver. In order to prevent such unfortunate incidents from happening, it would be appropriate to explain to our children the rules of the correct movement on the roads from the time of kindergarten and school, explaining the consequences. It is important for parents to set an example for their children when driving on the roads. We can see in statistical data

that urgent problems such as road traffic accidents and the release of toxic gases by vehicles into the environment are increasing over the years in the territory of Uzbekistan.

Diagram 1

Some changes in road traffic incidents in 2020-2022

As can be clearly seen from the above diagram, the number of injured people has increased by 2500 in 3 years. We don't know how serious or light the injury is. It is natural that an injured person can join the society and continue working, and it takes enough time to return to a healthy lifestyle. And the number of dead people is variable, which means that medicine is rapidly developing over time? In any case, it is necessary for us to achieve the maximum result by using the methods, techniques and technologies developed by the specialists of the field and which are giving positive results in order to drastically reduce the number of dead people (to zero as much as possible). The number of people who hit a pedestrian also changed over the course of 3 years. But it continued to grow in recent years. This, like the reasons mentioned above, is caused by the lack of education of pedestrians and drivers. We should drastically reduce the numbers in the diagram above, apply the methods of developed countries to save people's lives from danger, share experience and certainly achieve the expected results.

References:

1. Усманов Р., Абдухамидов С. ПРИБЛИЖЕННОЕ РЕШЕНИЕ УРАВНЕНИЕ ГАРДНЕРА УПРОЩЕННЫМ МЕТОДОМ УКРОЧЕННЫХ РАЗЛОЖЕНИЙ //Фундаментальные и прикладные научные исследования: актуальные вопросы, достижения и инновации. – 2019. – С. 64-67.
2. Абдухамидов С. К., Омонов З. Ж. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СМАЗОЧНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ДИЗЕЛЕЙ ПЕРЕВЕДЁННЫХ НА СЖАТЫЙ ПРИРОДНЫЙ ГАЗ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 3-1. – С. 387-390.
3. Abduxamidov S. TWO-STEP IMPLICIT PISMAN-RICKFORD SCHEME FOR SOLVING THE LAPLACE EQUATION //Eurasian Journal of Mathematical Theory and Computer Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 29-30.

4. Маликов З. М. и др. ЧИСЛЕННОЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ТЕЧЕНИЯ В ПЛОСКОМ ВНЕЗАПНО РАСШИРЯЮЩЕМся КАНАЛЕ НА ОСНОВЕ ДВУХЖИДКОСТНОЙ МОДЕЛИ ТУРБУЛЕНТНОСТИ И МОДЕЛИ УИЛКОКСА //Проблемы машиноведения. – 2021. – С. 204-211.

5. www.lex.uz

